

Performance of public administrations in the Covid era

La performance des administrations publiques à l'ère du Covid

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Abstract

In an already strained economic context, the recent appearance of devastating crises that followed the worldwide spread of Covid 19, has created many challenges to all organizations, from public or private sector, hindering their ability to prosper and be efficient. Today more than ever, performance is at the heart of the attention of many organizations' strategies and action plans. In 2011, the Moroccan government has launched multiple reforms aiming to modernize the public sector that led to the institution of the new organic law n°130-13 related to the finance law (LOF). This law placed performance as one of its main pillars through a shift from a logic of means to one set around results. It has also promoted the principals of good governance and reinforced the role of supervisory authorities to guarantee performance in the public sphere and ensure the cohesion of public policies. The functioning of public administrations went from a strictly legal and technical approach to one favoring managerial culture at the service of citizens. The concept of performance has greatly evolved through the evolution of management theories and with the occurrence of the pandemic, one can therefore ask how performance of public administrations is perceived and measured. In this context, this article aims to examine through a literary review around the concept of performance, the impact of the Covid 19 pandemic on the performance of Moroccan and European public administrations.

Keywords: performance; Covid 19; performance measurement; Organic law (LOF); performance approach.

Résumé

Dans un contexte économique déjà tendu, l'apparition récente de crises dévastatrices qui ont suivi la propagation mondiale du Covid 19 a créé de nombreux défis pour toutes les organisations du secteur public ou privé, entravant leur capacité à prospérer et à être efficaces. Aujourd'hui plus que jamais, la performance est au cœur de l'attention des stratégies et des plans d'action de nombreuses organisations. En 2011, le gouvernement marocain a lancé un chantier de réformes visant à moderniser le secteur public qui a été couronné par l'institution de la nouvelle loi organique n° 130-13 relative à la loi de finances (LOF). Cette loi a fait de la performance l'un de ses principaux piliers, et a remplacé la gestion publique basée sur la logique des moyens par celle des résultats. Elle a également promu, les principes de la bonne gouvernance, renforcé le rôle des autorités de tutelle pour garantir la performance de la sphère publique et assurer la cohérence des politiques publiques. A cet effet, le fonctionnement des administrations publiques est passé d'une approche strictement juridique et technique à une approche privilégiant la culture managériale au service des citoyens. Le concept de la performance a beaucoup évolué et suite à l'apparition de la pandémie, on peut donc se demander comment la performance des administrations publiques est perçue et mesurée. Dans ce contexte, cet article a pour objectif d'examiner, à travers une revue de littérature autour du concept de la performance, l'impact de la pandémie du Covid 19 sur la performance des administrations publiques marocaines et européennes.

Mots clés : performance ; Covid 19 ; mesure de la performance ; loi organique (LOF) ; approches de la performance.

Introduction

In 2020, the pandemic of COVID-19 grew to reach almost every country on the planet, affecting the lives of millions of people Worldwide. Making it, the deadliest pandemic to plague the human kind since the Spanish flu that broke early in the 20th century. In a context full of uncertainty and precariousness, public administrations had to operate many arbitrations on the economic and social levels, in order to face the hardships posed by the pandemic. During early March 2020, as a way to put a damper to the spread of the disease, more than half of the world's nations went into lockdown, as well as instating a multitude of severe and restrictive measures changing the population's way of living by establishing the "stay home, stay safe" movement. Despite all the efforts, this pandemic had the most calamitous economical and financial repercussions on the world's economy since the Second World War. It comes as no surprise that, with the overall collapse of the global economy, Morocco has been affected. According to the International Monetary Fund, the gross domestic product, in 2020, has retracted by 7% due to lockdown measures and the drought that the country went through that year. The labor market, the financial market, the production line, were also seriously affected. Organizations everywhere had to rethink their performance models on the logistical, societal and financial levels, in order to align to the new economic situation posed by the virus.

Besides, in his speech of July 29, 2020, his majesty King Mohammed VI may god assist him, called for a profound reform of the public sector aiming, to correct the structural dysfunctions of public establishments and organizations, guarantee complementarity and coherence between their missions and enhance their economic and social efficiency. In this context, supervisory authorities have carried out various diagnoses which revealed that the development of public establishments is hindered by multiple impairments that have been exacerbated with the occurrence of the pandemic. Which begs the following question: How did the Covid 19 crisis affected the performance of public administrations?

To answer this question, this paper will analyze the concept of performance in public administrations, the assessment of performance in the context of crisis and the monitoring of performance, through a literary review. Subsequently, we will discuss the approach of performance in Moroccan public administrations and lastly, we will address the impact of COVID 19 on the performance of public administrations through a comparative analysis of the impact of the pandemic on Morocco and on countries from the European Union.

1. The concept of performance in public administrations

1.1. The concept of performance in literature

According to the Cambridge dictionary the term performance refers to «how well a person, machine, etc. does meaning that performance is an evaluation of the execution of an activity. In this context, the concept of performance is polysemic and its definition depends on the scope of activity covered (Bouazza & Lakchiri, 2020). For example, in sports, the performance of an athlete is defined by the results obtained to achieve an activity, the results can be measured by different variables such as distance, time, ranking or ratings. Within an organization, performance can be determined by measuring different variables that help define the settings of environment. For instance in mechanics, performance indicates the technical abilities of a machine to complete the desired tasks. In finance, performance is perceived as the evaluation of the company's effectiveness by examining its assets, liabilities, equity, expenses and revenues through different ratios and analysis of the financial statements.

Performance can therefore be defined as, « an official report recording a result that has been accomplished at a Time T, referring to a context, an objective and an expected result regardless of the field » (Notat, 2007).

In literature, scholars denied the existence of a unique definition to the notion of performance emphasizing on its multidimensional and layered nature. However, as a consensus, it could be agreed upon that performance is often linked and associated to the terms of efficiency and effectiveness.(Gibert, 1980) presented, as shown in Figure 1, performance in a triangle among the notions of objectives, means and results.

Figure 1: The triangle of performance

Source : Gibert, P. (1980).

-**The axis objectives-results:** represents the notion of effectiveness which is an indicator for achieving the desired results within a framework of set objectives.

- **The axis Means- results:** represents the notion of efficiency which is the ratio between the output (effort produced) and the input or the means engaged in an activity in order to achieve the desired outcome. In other words, efficiency refers to the achievement of results at the lowest cost.

- **The axis Objectives-Means:** represents relevance which is the ratio between the engaged means and the objectives that are set to be achieved. It measures the allocation of resources.

Similarly, (Hoffman, 1999) defines the notion of performance as a mean to evaluate the level of fulfillment of organizational objectives. To which, (Krause, 2005) added that performance indicates the degree of fulfillment of the objectives or desired results, defined according to a specific criteria and set by the organization's stakeholders. Furthermore, the use of the word performance is still very controversial, since in 2001, (Otley,2001) stated "The word 'performance' is something of a weasel word , in that it appears to mean very different things to different people, thus we use it quite freely, apparently understanding its meaning, but actually often using it to cover a lack of shared understanding".

1.2. Performance in public administrations:

In literature, two approaches to the concept of public performance management stand out: economic oriented approach and stakeholders' approach

1.2.1. Economic oriented approach to performance:

This approach focuses on the input-output-outcome (IOO) model, where outcomes are quantified by non-financial indicators represented by the social profits obtained from an action. Outputs, on the other hand, don't necessarily fall into the desired or expected outcomes. This model includes the components of the 3E model: economy (implemented in the inputs), efficiency (quantifies the outputs to inputs ratio) and effectiveness (integrated in the outcomes). Another complementary approach to the 3E model is advanced by the New Public Management (NPM) current. NPM focuses not only on the inputs and outputs but also on the customer's perspective. (Hood, 1995) introduced five principals to help the public understand, how the concept of performance can be derived from the essence of NPM:

- Introducing result based management, which upgraded the role played by administrators to managers responsible for results.

- Using a gauge of the effects of actions, this implies the definition of the strategic goals of the local administration, the contribution of its partners and the enhancement of the transmission of information among them.
- Shifting the focus on the client's or user's satisfaction making the public service fit to meet their needs.
- Setting the best outlook to public finances through cost analysis, outsourcing or privatization of specified facilities.
- Instituting transparency and accuracy of public accounts, similar to the norms imposed to the companies in the private sector, administrations are called to properly set balance sheets that represent accurate valuation of their assets and to certify their accounts by external auditors.

1.2.2. Stakeholders' oriented approach to performance

The stakeholder or partnership approach to performance consists of incorporating the citizen's standpoints in the performance measuring process. There are two models based on this approach: The common Assessment Framework (CAF) and the Public Sector Scorecard.

- The Common assessment Framework (CAF): is a framework that was established in 2006 through the cooperation between the European Public Administration Network (EUPAN), EIPA and European ministers in charge of public administrations. This model focuses on installing good governance in the public sector and prioritizing innovation, digitalization, sustainability and variety. It's a holistic approach to examine organizational performance that aims to provide adequate public services that are appealing to the citizens or customers; performance is then measured by the number of complaints received or the level of commitment made during the service. It also emphasizes on the social impact of results on the society and the organization's environment.
- Public Sector Balanced Scorecard (BSC): This model was introduced by (Moullin, 2002) with the intent to *"provide an overall framework for performance measurement and service improvement, adapting the BSC to the culture and values of the public and semi-public sectors"*. The main objective of this model is to incorporate stakeholders in the setting objectives by aligning the organization's strategy to the needs and

expectations of users and stakeholders. Therefore, performance is measured by the satisfaction of users and their perception of the service.

1.3. Performance assessment in the context of crisis:

According to the Cambridge dictionary, the term “crisis” refers to a: “*time of great disagreement, confusion*” (Cambridge dictionary). Comparably, scholars have defined the word “crisis” as an unusual and complex state that threatens the operating system of an organization. (Fink, 2002) described the word crisis as an abnormal situation that endangers the functioning, the well-being and the image of an organization. A crisis is also perceived as a non-expected event that menaces or is considered to endanger an organization’s critical objectives (Boins, et al., 2005). (MacFarlane, 2010) stated that crisis is also considered as a menace to the values and norms of a structure, which under time of urgency and uncertainty impel making crucial decisions. (Coombs, 2012) declared that crisis is “*the perception of an unexpected event that threatens important expectancies of beneficiaries and can seriously affect an organisation’s performance and cause negative consequences*”. (Coombs, 2012).

In a common state, performance is the gathering of multiple aspects such as: relevancy, flexibility, efficiency, effectiveness, responsiveness, resilience and flexibility (Marcon, & al., 2003) that help the decision making process. For instance, efficiency demonstrates how well the resources were managed in order to achieve the desired results. When a difficulty regarding efficiency occurs, it signals that more efforts are needed to improve the management of resources. Hence, in the case of a crisis it is important to distinguish the dimensions that will overrule.

Figure 2: Framework of crisis performance assessment

Source: Carine, et al ., (2013)

In a context of crisis, performance assessment must consider a handful of characteristics that can be defined as follows:

- Objectives: which are the goals and targets to attain, that are identified by indicators which control the level of their achievement.
- Means: which are the resources and assets used on an operational level.
- Results: which are the outcomes of systems and operations.
- Beneficiaries/Donators: refer to the person who pays to acquire the product/service.

As showcased in the framework (figure 2), performance can be assessed in a crisis situation through different dimensions:

- Impact: represents the linkage between the means, objectives and results.
- Efficiency: represents the means to results ratio.
- Relevance: represents the adequation of means regarding the objectives.
- Expectations: represents the needs and prospects of beneficiaries.
- Satisfaction: indicates if the expectations of beneficiaries were met.
- Agility: represents the aggregation of flexibility, reactivity and effectiveness.

2. The approach of performance in Moroccan public administrations

2.1. The approach to performance

During the last two decades, the Moroccan government has launched several political, financial, sectorial and economic reforms aiming to boost the national economy and align to the expanding needs of its citizens. This focus has led to various measures centered on the principals of good governance and transparency particularly in terms of public finances, through the obligation to ensure accountability, control and evaluate public funds.

The new organic Law n°130-13 related to the law of Finances has instituted new directives regarding the elaboration and execution of the state budget focusing on, the reinforcement of the performance of public management, most notably by transitioning from a means based management to a performance based management. Also, though the introduction of a three-year budget programming format, making it easier to help track the budget in a three-year horizon. Therefore, the approach to performance in public structures could be detailed as follows:

- **Presentation of the ministry's strategy:**

The strategy must rely on, an internal diagnosis of the strengths, weaknesses of the sector in which the ministry intervenes and, on the opportunities, and threats of the environment of the sector (economic, social, environmental...). The strategy must be as concise and precise as possible, it has to be comprehensible by the decision-makers, stakeholders and the public. It has to highlight the most important axes, dubbed “strategic axes”, showcased by the ministry to assemble and set up its action in the three years to come.

- **Translation of ministry strategy into programs:**

The strategy has to be translated into a limited number of cohesive programs. According to Article 39 of the LOF “A program is an ensemble of cohesive projects or actions belonging to the same ministerial department or the same institution, to which objectives are associated and defined as to serve general interest and contains a number of indicators to measure the expected results.

- **Definition of the program’s strategy:**

The program’s strategy has to be set according to a three years framework, with a set of predefined objectives and action plans to achieve the said objectives. Moreover, the strategy has to include an analysis of the potential obstacles for the fixed objectives, a reminder of the degree of public interest associated to the policy and a presentation of the action plan from which leaders intend to execute the strategy.

- **Selection of the program’s objectives:**

The objectives of programs have to be representative of the overall essence of the program which has to serve the general interest of citizens, upgrade the service provided to the users and optimize the effectiveness of the administration’s output.

- **Identification of indicators of performance:**

Each objective has to be connected to one or multiple quantified indicators enabling the assessment of the achieved results. These indicators could be a ratio, a percentage, proportion, etc. However, for auditing purposes, the choice of each indicator has to be documented within an instruction form in order to understand the nature, the scope and the periodicity of data gathering.

2.2. Performance monitoring

Performance monitoring is a systematic examination of performance over time that consists of collecting, analyzing and restituting performance indicators and records aiming to assess the achievement of performance objectives. It helps to display effective and ineffective operations, track underperformance and identify future needs which avoid the replication of ineffective acts. Moreover, performance monitoring is a part of the budgetary procedure. Its objective is to direct budgeting decisions and provide insights in the budget making process. It acts as a connector between the ministry, the direction of budget and the parliament. The monitoring of performance can be documented in:

- **The Performance Project:** presents a comparison between the forecasts showcased in the finance bill (N+1) and the finance law N and (N-1), it exposes the reasoning behind the strategic decisions, the expected results and the indicators. The performance project is prepared by the sectorial ministry and contains the objectives of performance along with the indicators. It exposes for each program the differences between the forecasts of the previous years (N-1) and the objectives aimed to be achieved in the finance bill of the ongoing year. The performance project holds managers accountable for the execution of the programs previously announced and for the achievement of objectives.
- **The Performance Report:** presents a review of the execution of the strategy of the ministry, underlines the execution of the budget of the ministry for each program and action plan and displays the performance of the programs in terms of objectives and indicators attained.

Furthermore, performance monitoring is also tracked through a performance audit based on norms and international best practices. These norms help to set a structured approach that leads to conclusive observations and recommendations to redress potential dysfunctional management.

The Inspectorate General of Finance IGF, has developed an audit manual, which is registered in the installment of the budgetary reform, that is focused on the results and sets the terms and policies needed to conduct the audit. The main objectives behind that manual are, to guarantee the quality of the performance audit, install common working methods adapted to the assignment, and ensure an appropriate communication of the results to the managers. In addition to that, the monitoring of performance could be done through management control,

mainly balanced scorecards which are valuable for the deployment strategies and other effective decision making tools. The balanced scorecard uses key performance indicators (KPI), which are critical to achieve the intended results. KPI are, quantifiable measures that have to be explicit, aligned with the objectives of the organization, limited and identified by operational and strategic actors in order to assess the progress made toward the fulfillment of the strategy and vision of the organization.

3. The impact of Covid 19 on the performance of public administrations

The eruption of the coronavirus pandemic has been an unparalleled event that governments all across the globe have never experienced before. The alarming pace with which the virus spread, has led governments to rethink the operating systems used in public administrations in order to ensure the continuity and quality of the delivered services. The following paragraph is a comparative analysis of the decisions made by the Moroccan government and the European Union governments regarding the following aspects: management of human resources, management of the public expenditures and public services.

3.1. Management of human resources:

The social distancing and logistic restrictions that came with it, has led to the application of new working methods and arrangements such as teleworking. Matter of fact, the physical presence in the work premises remained limited to when the task or operation required it. In order to structure and facilitate the working from home initiative, the Ministry of the Economy, Finance and Administration Reform of Morocco has published in April 2020 a guide on remote working for public administrations, presenting the commitments needed from both, the administrations and the civil servants, as well as the mechanisms needed to guarantee the continuity of public services.

In the countries where lockdown measures were enforced, the majority of civil servants were telecommuting, some of the activities that were deemed not important were suspended during the peak of the pandemic, and others weren't able to use telecommute working due to the lack of infrastructure or privacy and data security. A survey conducted by the department of Administrative Reform of Morocco in collaboration with the World Bank, revealed that 58% of civil servants¹ were unable to perform certain tasks outside of their office due to lack of

¹ Participants are civil servants/directors from 17 Ministries, Haut- au Plan (HCP), Haut - Commissariat aux Anciens Résistants et Anciens Membres de l'Armée de Libération Commissariat and from the Délégation Générale à l'Administration Pénitentiaire et à la Réinsertion.

resources and equipment and 18% were obligated to go to their workplace to ensure privacy and data security.

In some countries such as Belgium, France and Portugal, civil servants who can't fulfill their jobs, could be exempted and placed in special leave, while retaining their rights and full salary. Latvia is the only country in the world where "the wait for work" policy is applied to civil servants who can't telecommute, upon the decision of their superior and perceiving 80% of their average salary for the preceding three months.

A lot of countries have adopted flexible working systems and authorized shifting from telecommuting and working from the office space. During lockdown, 42% of Moroccan civil servants worked by alternating between office hours and working from home, 30% of Moroccan civil servants worked strictly from their office and 27% of them worked strictly from home.

Despite the disturbance caused by the pandemic, most directors (49%) believe that the performance of their units hasn't changed due to Covid, 26% believe that it declined and 25% declared an increase in performance. The pandemic also impacted the workload of civil servants although not in every public administration. The survey concluded that 43% of Moroccan civil servants declared an expansion in their workload, 37% stated that it remained the same, and 20% noted a decrease in workload.

If flexible working hours were adopted by multiples countries such as Austria, most civil servants telecommuted during the usual and normal hours. Thus their working hours remained unchanged. For others, working hours were rearranged as to deal with rush hours. In Morocco 40% of civil servants benefited from reduced working hours, 36% of civil servants have declared that their working hours remained unchanged and 24% have seen an increase of their working timetable.

Since the start of the pandemic, some countries have increased the salaries of civil servants who performed their jobs under dangerous circumstances. In Slovenia, this compensation was applied from 45% up to 100% of the working hours performed under dangerous circumstances. Other countries like Belgium and Netherlands gave bonuses and compensations for the medical staff, which is also the case for Morocco which provided an exceptional bonus ranging from 2500 DH up to 9000 DH to the staff involved directly or indirectly in the medical field (doctors, pharmacists, professor of CHU ,technicians...etc.).

3.2. Management of public expenditures

In March 22th 2020, the European council has announced that the ministries of Finances of the State Members had approved the evaluation of the Commission regarding the usage of the general backup of the European budget frame. It also concluded that, the pandemic would cause a slow economic growth in the European Union, which in consequence would make the budget deficit exceed the GDP growth by approximately 3%. The ministries agreed to respect the pact of stability and growth, but the general backup frame would allow the commission and council to take the needed measures concerning the political coordination of the pact without respecting the budgetary requirements that would normally be applied due to the alarming economic consequences of the pandemic.

As declared from The International Monetary Fund, in order to manage the economic backlash of the pandemic, the public financial management systems had to facilitate the redefinition of priorities in terms of expenditures to ensure liquidity and to cover financial needs, to put in place mechanisms based on transparency and accounting that enable public managers to get valuable and important data for decision making. In this context many governments have proactively reacted by implementing different actions.

The measures taken by some EU governments in order to deal with the pandemic and help the recovery of the economy are established as follow:

- Increase in the budget allocated to the health department in terms of equipment, staff, medication, etc.
- Increase in the budget allocated to social security to aid the payment for the expanding number of unemployed due to the pandemic;
- Provide business grants and loans to help enterprises manage their obligations due to lockdown;
- Institute tax deferral for corporations and small business.

Similarly, the Moroccan government has adopted a proactive approach to minimize the impact caused by the pandemic. Back in March 15th 2020, the government proceeded under the instructions of his Majesty King Mohamed IV, to create a Fund (which was valued in May 2020 to approximately 3,3 billion USD) designed to face the consequences of the pandemic, which was managed by the watch Economy Committee. Chaired by the Ministry of Economy, Finances and the Reform of Administration and has been installed in March 16th 2020,

including different ministerial departments, the Central Bank and organizations hailing from the private sector. The principal mission of the said committee was to control the economic situation through rigorous mechanisms of monitoring, evaluating and identifying the appropriate demands to support the sectors impacted by the crisis. Some of the notorious measures taken by the Moroccan government are presented as follows:

- Granting of a monthly allowance of 2000 DH for employees in partial or total unemployment affiliated to the social security system (CNSS). The supported action by the Fund has approximated 6,3 billion of Dirhams in June 2020;
- Payment of allowances to nearly 5.5 Million of households operating in the informal sector (an allowance ranging from 800 DH to 1200 DH);
- Reduction of social, financial and tax charges for the warfare of companies completed by the suspension of the payment of social security contributions due to the social security system (CNSS) from March 1st to June 30th 2020;
- Loans reaching up to 15 000 DH with zero interest for the sake of auto entrepreneurs that were affected by the pandemic;
- Flexibility of procedures and operations for companies holding public contracts;
- Acceleration of the implementation of the dispositions of the reforms of the administration through the simplification of administration procedures and the reinforcement of digitalization in the administration operations.

3.3. Public services

Public services have undoubtedly been disturbed by the surfacing of Covid 19, specifically administrative services. Due to lockdown, public administrations had to rethink their functioning systems to make sure that the citizen's needs were met. Since the majority of civil servants were telecommuting, providing public services was done mainly via electronic means, such as e-mail, online registers, telephones, etc. In order to help administrations delivering public services, some European countries have established some operating systems such as:

- Portugal: The Agency for the administrative modernization collaborated with municipalities in order to provide guidelines to administrations with the intention to communicate daily on the available and unavailable service points which help citizens navigate through public services during the pandemic.

- Italy: the decree “curaitalia” was enacted by the Italian government on March 17th 2020 and specified the public services that were available to the citizens all throughout the Italian territory.
- Czech Republic: The general director of the public function recommended to public organizations to limit all activities that weren’t correlated to the emergency measures or to the daily life of citizens and to limit opening hours.

In all countries, there have been increasing uses of IT tools, video conferences for meetings and exchange of information. In Romania, the applications submitted for social assistance benefits such as state allowances for children and unemployed, could be sent by mail or email. In Slovenia, they simplified the communication between administrations and citizens by allowing them to send documents via mail or emails and if any civil servant had doubts concerning the identity of a subject they would require a scanned copy of the document with a handwritten signature to be sent by email.

Similarly, Morocco has taken proactive actions to face the events caused by Covid 19 allowing users to submit some documents and to complete some formalities online. In fact, The Social Security System (CNSS) has created an online platform which allowed employers to declare their situation and employees who are suspended from work. In Morocco the digital signature is governed by the Dahir n°1-07-129 of November 30th, 2007 promulgating the law n° 53-05 related to electronic exchange of legal data. The Article 6 of the said law indicates that digital signatures have to meet certain requirements: it has to be distinct to the signatory, be created by means that the signatory can control, be attached to a link ensuring that any subsequent modification is detectable and it also has to be built by an electronic signature creation device attested by a certificate of conformity delivered by “Barid AL-Maghrib”. A digital order office has been established to allow the deposit against receipt of administrative correspondence. The platform “rokhas.ma” has simplified procedures regarding the opening of businesses during the pandemic by allowing applicants to submit applications for authorization electronically, as well as for those applications to be signed by the president of the municipality.

The Moroccan government has also implemented a new specific mechanism called “Damane oxygen” intended to guarantee exceptional cash overdrafts to be granted in favor of companies whose cashflow has been strongly affected by the pandemic and which turnover hasn’t exceeded 200 Million Dirhams. The said product enfolds 95% of the loans and enables

companies to cope with operational expenditure which cannot be deferred or suspended (such as salaries, rent...etc). On July 2020, 45 000 companies nearly have profited from “Damane oxygen” for an outstanding amount of 17 Billion Dirhams.

Conclusion

Over the past decade, the concept of performance in public administrations has been invoked in miscellaneous settings (administrative, political, social...etc), and with the spread of Covid 19, the importance of performance in the public sphere was heightened. Therefore, through this paper, we tried to examine the impact of Covid 19 on the performance of public administrations.

Firstly, we presented a literary review around the concept of performance which showed that performance is multidimensional, polysemic and can be used in various settings. Then we presented the approach to the concept of public performance management, discussed by scholars: the economic oriented approach to performance and the stakeholder approach to performance. Afterward we analyzed the notion of performance assessment in the context of a crisis.

Secondly, we presented the approach of performance in Moroccan public administrations. Which is derived from the commands of the organic law n°130-13 related to the law of Finance which focuses on the performance of public management. Then, we displayed the concept of performance monitoring which consists of the examination of performance over a period of time through audits that help redress potential dysfunctions.

Lastly, we examined the impact of Covid 19 on the performance of public administrations through a comparative analysis of the decisions made by the Moroccan government and the European Union governments regarding the management of human resources, management of public expenditures and public services. Through this analysis, we concluded that the European and Moroccan government have adopted teleworking as a new working method to ensure the continuity of activities. When lockdown and movement have been restricted, they have taken budgetary decisions to support the financial damages caused by the pandemic and have encouraged the digitalization of vital public services.

The occurrence of this pandemic has brought new ways of working and organization of the public management. Under the circumstances imposed by the pandemic, the modernization of public administrations has been accelerated as the majority of administrations have adopted

telecommuting and operated through the usage of digital systems. Thanks to the crisis the public administrations have become haphazardly agile since new protocols and guidelines ruled remote working, simplifying processes and programs. Surely, the advantages of digitalization of public services are endless starting from establishing, accessibility, velocity and overall an improvement of performances. However, the digitalization of public services is also attached to the citizen's privacy and data protection and it implies that public administrations must dispose of the financial and human resources needed to ensure that the needs of citizens are met safely. Therefore, it would be appropriate to study the impact of digitalization on public administrations.

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